

Confidence intervals of inversely identified material model parameters: A novel two-stage error propagation model based on stereo DIC system uncertainty

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ABSTRACT

Digital image correlation (DIC) is a powerful tool for characterising materials and determining material model parameters. To assess the reliability of the full-field measurement-based inverse identification procedures, it is crucial to investigate the impact of the measurement errors on the identified material model parameters. Literature indicates that conventional error propagation models, which rely on Gaussian noise-contaminated data, significantly overestimate the confidence for inversely identified material model parameters, resulting in misleadingly narrow confidence intervals. A more precise assessment of systematic errors originating from the experimental setup leads to an improved prediction of the confidence intervals, but this requires specific information about the DIC equipment, post-processing details, and a skilled experimentalist. In this work, we propose an alternative two-stage error propagation model that yields more realistic confidence interval predictions based solely on a database of past mechanical experiments conducted with the specific stereo DIC system set up in a particular way. We have validated the proposed procedure numerically using the open-hole test and an orthotropic elastic material model. Our predictions reveal a non-Gaussian probability distribution of the inversely identified material model parameters, with confidence intervals considerably wider than those obtained by considering random Gaussian noise. Furthermore, these predictions were experimentally validated in an extensive experimental campaign investigating a pultruded carbon fibre epoxy composite.

1. Introduction

The reliability of numerical analyses is strongly affected by material modelling and the associated characterization procedure. While the material model plays a crucial role in the description of the physical material response, it is formulated to model a particular material behaviour for a range of unique materials, i.e. elasticity for a wide range of different composites, steels etc. The adaptability of the material model is achieved with a set of material parameters which define the behaviour of the modelled material. A calibration strategy is necessary to tune the model against experimental data. It involves identifying such material parameter values that the modelled responses agree with the measured ones. Conventionally, macroscopic mechanical material characterization relies on standard tests, such as uniaxial tensile, uniaxial compression, shear, and biaxial tests. However, increasing the complexity of the models leads to an increase in the number of material

parameters, and the concomitant need to identify the escalating number of parameters from these tests is a significant drawback [1,2]. The growth in the number of parameters corresponds to a mounting challenge in accurately measuring them through suitable experiments [3].

One of the options for identifying these parameters is performing a series of standard tests, which increases experimental effort. Alternatively, full-field measurement techniques like digital image correlation (DIC), at least in principle, enable the determination of parameters through a single heterogeneous strain field test using an inverse identification technique. It is therefore necessary to design a heterogeneous strain field specimen and a loading configuration, as well as to formulate a testing procedure that enables reliable parameter identification.

To assess the reliability of the identification procedure, a given set of measurements, which are accompanied by systematic and random errors, are often used to establish confidence intervals of the inversely identified material model parameters. Many studies have aimed to

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assess the influence of systematic and random error on the predicted confidence levels. Wang et al. [4], for example, analysed the influence of the entire measurement and data processing procedure by analysing synthetic images using DIC. Utilizing the Virtual Fields Method (VFM) algorithm, they predicted the confidence intervals of the identified parameters based on systematic and random errors obtained from simulations. In their study, predictions from virtual experiments were verified against physical experiments, revealing that, due to other sources of random and systematic errors, which were not considered in their research, the error was not reduced as anticipated. Marek et al. [5] used Gaussian white noise with a standard deviation of $150\mu\epsilon$ added to the strain data obtained from the finite element simulation to identify elasto-plastic parameters. They demonstrated that the noise level they chose is a reasonable assumption for a well-designed and properly conducted experiment. However, this is only a first approach to noise propagation simulation. The authors proposed that an image deformation procedure is necessary to realistically simulate both systematic and random errors (e.g. presented in [6] and [4]). A similar study has been conducted by Chalal et al. [7], who applied Gaussian white noise to synthetic data to analyse the influence of the choice of virtual fields in the VFM and demonstrated that this assumption is too simplistic. They assumed that the noise at different measurement locations is uncorrelated. Such simplification was needed to keep the process analytical. It should be emphasized that the presented approaches rely on synthetic data; it is well-known that in actual measurements, there are other sources of systematic and random errors [8,9].

The need for realistic confidence intervals has also been demonstrated by Rossi et al. [6], who analysed the effect of spatial resolution, noise and interpolation error in DIC on the identification results. This was the first step towards providing a framework for the quantification of uncertainty through the use of heterogeneous tests, full-field measurements and inverse identification. The authors introduced Gaussian white noise to the grey level value of each synthetically deformed image. This was the first rational approach to the selection of the optimal DIC setup and parameters. Badaloni et al. [10] improved the simulator by including all principal sources of error to bridge the gap between experimental uncertainties and the inversely identified material model parameters. To tackle the problem, they studied and disentangled the influence of image noise, out-of-plane movements, in-plane movements and illumination on the identified parameters. Under controlled conditions, they showed that the identification of linear elasticity constants is impaired mainly due to out-of-plane movements, with only minor contribution from other sources. The metrological performance of full-field measurement techniques is now better known [11] and the efforts in quantifying the error effects on predicted material parameters have mainly focused on the quantification of the error effects of lens distortion [12–16], misalignment of cameras [17,18], camera noise [19–21], and speckle patterns [22–26], algorithmic treatment [27–30], image noise and others. It should be noted that in the DIC configurations used in practice it is difficult to identify and quantify the sources of errors, as they are user-dependent and may vary depending on the DIC settings within the same experiment. Even more, when considering the separate contributions of different DIC parameters as sources of potential error to the prediction of confidence intervals, the parameters co-vary and this is usually not considered in the analyses [31]. Additionally, not all errors are normal in distribution [21,32].

The purpose of this study is to assess the DIC measurements error based on real DIC measurement data while taking into account various error sources throughout the measurement procedure, from the application of speckle pattern (a process that is highly user-dependent), through lens distortions, to cameras misalignment etc., and to determine their effect on the confidence intervals of the inversely identified material model parameters. As discussed above, the influence of random error or the individual influences of systematic errors associated with different DIC settings on the inversely identified material model parameters are frequently reported in the literature. The errors are

generated from generic uncertainty input or are synthesized under controlled DIC parameters conditions. It should be emphasized that the experimentalist or DIC user is usually unaware of these sources of errors and DIC parameters are not set optimally or fully controlled when conducting an actual experiment. Accordingly, we hypothesized that the confidence intervals typically presented in literature might not be realistic.

We tackle the problem by first analysing 850 stereo-DIC measurements, which represent our entire measurement history using our stereo DIC system, spanning different experimental setups and various specimens. All our measurements follow the same measuring protocol. Specimens are first coloured matt white with black speckles. The stereo-DIC equipment is set to measure the surface strains of the specimens, with the specimen preparation and DIC equipment setup carried out such that quality results are obtained, to the best of our ability.

Before loading the specimen, two still images of the region of interest are captured. These images are subsequently utilized in this work to compute means and standard deviations of measurement errors, detailed in Sect. 2. Even if the specimen exhibits prior deformations (e.g., because of thermal expansion, gravity, residual stresses), the state of the specimen in the moments of acquiring still images is unchanged. The measured strain field for these still images should therefore ideally be zero and any deviations are classified as errors. We subsequently explore how these characterized errors impact the identified material parameters. We do so employing a methodology proposed by Gras et al. [33], adapted for a strain-based finite element model updating (FEMU) identification procedure, outlined in Sect. 2.2.

The approaches described in the papers mentioned previously focus on the root causes of DIC-induced strain errors and evaluate how they propagate to the parameters identified. We deviate from such traditional bottom-up approaches by instead evaluating the strain uncertainty by analysing the previous results obtained using a particular measurement setup. For instance, in contrast to Marek et al. [5], who introduced a simple assumption of a strain error of $150\mu\epsilon$ added to an idealised finite element analysis strain field (FEM), our method employs a more elaborate and realistic two-stage error model to capture these inaccuracies. Rossi et al. [6] and Badaloni et al. [10] have dedicated considerable efforts to perform virtual experiments that involved virtually deforming an image of the sample, introducing errors, and subsequently utilizing it for strain evaluations using digital image correlation (DIC). By contrast, our method eliminates the need for the direct analysis of the images themselves, allowing rational adaptation to specific measurement systems. Moreover, our method embodies a unique “technical” approach that can already be used in the specimen design phase.

Using the two-stage error propagation model we have developed, we establish the confidence intervals for the parameters of the orthotropic elasticity model in Sect. 3. For this purpose, we used standard open-hole test for composite laminates testing [34]. In Sect. 4, the methodology is verified by executing 140 virtual experiments of the open-hole test, performing inverse identification of material parameters, and analysing the corresponding confidence intervals. Finally, the proposed methodology is validated in an extensive experimental campaign involving 140 open hole experiments conducted on pultruded carbon fibre epoxy composite specimens.

2. Methodology

2.1. Assessment of error distributions from past measurements

To get the most realistic information about measuring uncertainty—which can vary considerably based on experimental setups [35, 36]—we evaluated our stereo DIC system’s uncertainty using our existing measurements with no particular regard to the experiment type. The key takeaway is that this approach encompasses all the errors originating from the DIC equipment and the experimental setup, including specimen preparation, as well as the experimentalist operating

the system, who cannot be fully aware of all the potential sources of error.

In the proposed error evaluation, we followed an idea similar to the one used by Badaloni et al. [10]. After mounting a heterogeneous specimen with a speckle pattern in the testing machine, we acquire a series of images with the DIC measurement system before introducing any loads to the specimen. Since the testing machine is at rest, the strains measured should be zero after evaluating the images with DIC [37]. In contrast to [10], where the authors used 100 still images of the same static specimen, we evaluated a set of still images before loading for different specimens, DIC algorithm setup, equipment settings and loading configurations. We processed 850 individual measurements from our private archive, without any classification by experiment type. We considered all experimental setups, like standard uniaxial, open hole, notched, three/four-point bending specimen tests and others. In all our recording procedures, the first two sets of pictures were acquired before the testing machine started loading the specimen.

For a particular experimental setup, we reconstructed the full-field surface strains using regular subset-based stereo DIC (Fig. 1). Since the strain field should be zero, we can treat the measured values as the error of that particular measurement. To use this information in further analysis, we assessed the probability cumulative distribution for each measured strain component (ε_{xx} , ε_{yy} , ε_{xy}) across the measured field and found that we can closely approximate the distribution of the measurement error with a Gaussian distribution $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma)$. Histograms with the corresponding distributions are shown in Fig. 1.

However, it would be misleading to generalize the error distribution from a single DIC test and pronounce it as characteristic for a measuring system since the errors are different from one setup to another [35]. To assess the error distribution that applies more generally to the measuring system, we reviewed all our existing measurements conducted in the past years with no particular time intervals. In all cases, the measurements were obtained using the same Dantec Dynamics Q-400 DIC measuring system. The system consists of two 2 Mpx digital cameras with 35 mm focal length lenses, a synchronization time box and the Istra 4D (Dantec Dynamics) software for image processing. All speckle patterns consisted of a matt white background with matt black speckles, which were created using an airbrush. Each measurement contained several thousand measuring points. Most causes of uncertainty were considered, for example, a non-ideal speckle pattern, changes in lighting conditions, some optical distortions, camera noise, camera misalignment, out-of-plane and in-plane movements, calibration conditions of the DIC system, different subset sizes, as well as user errors.

To include this information in further analyses, we analysed the errors in a two-stage procedure. In the first step, we analysed all 3 strain field components of stereo-DIC processed still images of an individual measurement and calculated the mean μ_i and the standard deviation σ_i of the analysed strain component separately (Fig. 2-left) for all measurements. The output of this step is a $3 \times m$ population of means μ_i and

standard deviations σ_i . In the second step, we analysed the population of means and standard deviations separately and created two histograms of probability distributions from the population of means μ_i and standard deviations σ_i for all different setups and specimen configurations from our private archive. Finally, we approximated them with probability distribution laws, as presented in Fig. 2 (right). In contrast to [10], where images of the same static specimen were used and the resulting distributions over 100 repetitions were found to be unbiased, we found that in our case, where different DIC setups were used, the measurements were biased.

The bias manifests as the population of means shown in Fig. 3a and has an impact on the inverse identification of material model parameters. The population of the standard deviations of errors is typically asymmetrical and is presented in Fig. 3b.

Finally, we approximated the calculated distributions with a probability distribution law, so we can use the information from our past experiments in further calculations and numerical prediction of confidence intervals. The approximation of the probability distribution of the means of the errors \mathcal{S}_μ is a generalized hyperbolic (GH) distribution with parameters $\{0.0425978, 2498.15, 0, 4.58485 \times 10^{-6}, 4.74097 \times 10^{-6}\}$. The approximation of the standard deviations of the errors \mathcal{S}_σ is a Log-Normal distribution with the mean and standard deviation parameters -6.3 and 1.8 , respectively. Finally, it should be emphasized that in our case, the measured populations encompass not only random noise, but also other systematic errors associated with the experimental setup and the stereo DIC system, which are incorporated in the population of the mean value. Since for individual strain field measurements the systematic errors co-vary with experimental setup, it is essential for the error assessment to remain a two-stage procedure. (cf. Fig. 2).

2.2. Influence of error on the identified parameters

To investigate the impact of the measured strains accompanied by systematic and random errors on the identification results, the material parameters' confidence intervals were assessed by applying a procedure proposed by Gras et al. [33]. The derivation of the confidence interval assessment expression can also be found in some preceding studies, see e.g. [38,39], which served as the basis for the implementation of the proposed two-stage error propagation model.

Herein we use the strain-based FEMU method, which is essentially a method solving the least-squares-(LSQ) optimization problem on the DIC strain measurements. In the procedure, an output of the finite element method (FEM) model writes the data vector $\varepsilon_c(\theta)$ at N acquisition points as nodal strain. The vector θ represents a set of parameters of the constitutive model. Let us also denote the measured strains at acquisition points as ε_m , and the optimal material parameters to be predicted by the LSQ optimization as $\hat{\theta}$. Measured data ε_m can be related to FE model output data $\varepsilon_c(\theta)$ as

Fig. 1. Spatial distributions (above) and cumulative probability distributions (below) of strain measurement errors, determined from still images. Figures from left to right correspond to individual strain component ε_{xx} , ε_{yy} and ε_{xy} , respectively.

Fig. 2. Assessment of strain errors based on past DIC measurements (history) in a two-stage procedure. For individual strain field measurement, the error is modelled using a Gaussian distribution (Step 1 - figure left). Since these distributions vary from one experiment to another, the means and standard deviations of Gaussian distributions for all measurements and all strain components are combined into the blue histograms (Step 2 - figure right).

Fig. 3. (a) and (b) display histograms of the measured population of $3 \times m$ means and standard deviations, respectively. These data are derived from the strain errors of DIC processed still images across m measurements and three strain field components. Accompanying each histogram is a fitted probability law, illustrating the data's distribution pattern.

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_m = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_c(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) + \boldsymbol{e}, \quad (1)$$

where \boldsymbol{e} in Eq. (1) represents the combined systematic and random measurement errors of $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_m$. In other words, in absence of measurement error \boldsymbol{e} , the FE model output $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_c(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}})$ at optimal parameters $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ would be an exact representation of the physical behaviour $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_m$, which is only an assumption.

In LSQ optimization, our goal is to find values of the parameters $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ that best fit the given set of data by minimizing the 2-norm of the residuals of the misfit function $\boldsymbol{R}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_c(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_m$ [40]. We seek to minimize

$$S(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \|\boldsymbol{R}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\|^2 = \boldsymbol{R}(\boldsymbol{\theta})^T \boldsymbol{R}(\boldsymbol{\theta}). \quad (2)$$

Since we assume that the measurements include a random error and the system's bias, this causes a shift in the location of the minimum of the cost function S [41].

To exploit the influence of random error and the bias on the identified parameters, we investigate how small data perturbations influence the model's parameters [40]. For this purpose, we consider the first-order Taylor expansion of misfit function $\boldsymbol{R}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ in the neighbourhood of $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$

$$\boldsymbol{R}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \approx \boldsymbol{R}(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) + \boldsymbol{J}(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}})(\boldsymbol{\theta} - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}), \quad (3)$$

where \boldsymbol{J} represents the Jacobian matrix evaluated at $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$, which is assumed to be full rank [42]. Inserting Eq. (3) in Eq. (2) and assuming that relationship (1) holds, then Eq. (2) reads

$$S(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \|\boldsymbol{J}(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}})(\boldsymbol{\theta} - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) - \boldsymbol{e}\|^2 \quad (4)$$

A confidence interval crucially depends on the accuracy of the linearization [40] and is sensible only if $S(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is fairly flat in the neighbourhood of $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$. In practice, however, even if $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ is not known in advance,

its range of likely values usually is. If the variation of material parameters $\Delta\boldsymbol{\theta} = \boldsymbol{\theta} - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ is much smaller than their values, i.e., $\Delta\boldsymbol{\theta} \ll \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$, the linearization is valid even if the exact value of $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ is not known. By the same reasoning, we will carry out the Jacobian matrix \boldsymbol{J} calculations numerically, using a finite difference method.

By minimizing the cost function in Eq. (4), the solution of the linear LSQ optimization problem can be obtained from the linear relationship [43]

$$\Delta\boldsymbol{\theta} = \left((\boldsymbol{J}^T \cdot \boldsymbol{J})^{-1} \cdot \boldsymbol{J}^T \right) \cdot \boldsymbol{e} = \boldsymbol{K} \cdot \boldsymbol{e}, \quad (5)$$

where $\boldsymbol{K} = (\boldsymbol{J}^T \cdot \boldsymbol{J})^{-1} \cdot \boldsymbol{J}^T$ represents the coefficient matrix, dependent on the Jacobian matrix \boldsymbol{J} only.

By using Eq. (5), a calculation of the variation $\Delta\boldsymbol{\theta}$ for individual experimental data relies upon error \boldsymbol{e} that encapsulates systematic (bias) and random errors, explored in the previous section.

2.3. Error propagation analysis

Within the methodology, the influence of the characterized uncertainties on the material parameters can be explored, but since we adopted a sophisticated error model that features two-stage error assessment, we employed Monte Carlo (MC) simulations [31], where in each repetition generates new errors \boldsymbol{e} , and the expected variation in material parameters $\Delta\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is calculated using Eq. (5). The progression of the algorithm is schematically presented in the flowchart in Fig. 4. MC simulation, albeit robust, is also computationally-expensive [44]. As seen in Fig. 4, the coefficient matrix \boldsymbol{K} , which is quite expensive to compute, as it involves the inverse of a large matrix, can be calculated ahead of the MC loop, thereby eliminating one time-consuming calculation step usually associated with MC.

The result of the MC simulations is a large population of calculated

Fig. 4. Schematic progression of the algorithm for assessing the influence of the characterized uncertainties on the identified material parameters. By employing the FEM model sensitivity matrix and generating errors using MC simulations, a population of variations of material parameters is assessed.

material parameters' variations $\Delta\theta$. In ideal circumstances, $\Delta\theta$ would equal 0, but due to measurement errors e , a scatter in the population of material parameters is predicted. By calculating the margin of error (MOE) of the distribution with 68.3 % confidence, we get an estimate of the standard error associated with each material model parameter under investigation.

Fig. 4 also illustrates the workflow, which includes the generation of the experiment's FE model and one calculation of sensitivity matrix \mathbf{J} . To calculate the latter, we only need $1 + n$ FEM calculations, where n represents the number of material parameters. It should be emphasized that, since the coefficient matrix \mathbf{K} is calculated prior to performing the MC simulations, the MC iterations used to calculate the population of parameters' variations are computationally cheap. This approach improves the computational efficiency of assessing the parameter confidence intervals.

Introducing realistic random errors e represents one of the main challenges in MC simulations. We tackle this using a procedure that is the reverse of the one used to assess the uncertainties from the existing measurements described in the previous section (Fig. 5).

For each MC iteration, we first randomly sample the mean μ and standard deviation σ from the approximated probability distributions \mathcal{D}_μ and \mathcal{D}_σ to get the mean and the standard deviation for the current iteration:

$$\mu \sim \mathcal{D}_\mu, \sigma \sim \mathcal{D}_\sigma. \quad (6)$$

Each MC iteration is considered a separate measurement. In our case, these are DIC full-field strain measurements, which, as we have discovered, closely follow the Gaussian distribution $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma)$, where the mean and the standard deviation were determined from measurements (see Eq. (6)). We generate the random strain errors on the basis of the normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma)$ for n measurement values (three times the number of measuring points)

$$e_i = e \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma) \forall i = 1, \dots, n. \quad (7)$$

Eq. (7) yields error e , which we use in conjunction with Eq. (5) to assess the confidence intervals (cf. Fig. 4). It is worth noting that, while the generated errors incorporate most sources of error in DIC, the procedure does not consider errors originating from the correspondence between simulated and measured strains, like the mismatch error [45], load measurement error, speckle pattern degradation, FE model error (e. g., boundary conditions), material model error, and propagation of strain measurement error.

Fig. 5. Flowchart of the reverse procedure for the generation of the errors. For each MC simulation, a random sample of the mean and standard deviation is obtained for probability distributions \mathcal{D}_μ and \mathcal{D}_σ . Based on the obtained values, the strain field errors e_i are generated over the entire field of view.

2.4. Procedure overview and a guide for practical implementation

The developed methodology permits an assessment of the parameter's uncertainty and applies in principle to any heterogeneous strain field specimen measured with the stereo-DIC technique. The methodology consists of two main steps, as illustrated in the flowcharts in Fig. 2 and Fig. 4. Applying the method to a new measuring system, however, consists of 6 individual steps as outlined below.

1. Errors of the DIC system

We need to gather as many evaluations of still images as possible from an archive of past DIC measurements. Following the flowchart in Fig. 2, we first individually calculate the mean and the standard deviation associated with each experiment. Next, we approximate the probability distributions of the means and standard deviations calculated from the archive of past experimental data. The resulting probability distributions \mathcal{D}_μ and \mathcal{D}_σ are used in the 5th step.

2. FEM simulations

We need to calculate a reference specimen response $\epsilon_c(\theta)$ using a FEM simulation. Since we the true material parameter values are not known, we approximate them as best as we can (i.e., take them from literature, or identify them from previous measurements using FEMU). Additionally, we need to calculate the specimen response to the variation of a material parameter value $\epsilon_c(\theta + \delta\theta_i)$ for each i -th material parameter individually.

3. Sensitivity matrix

Using the responses calculated in the previous step, we can calculate the sensitivity (Jacobian) matrix \mathbf{J} as $j_i = (\epsilon_c(\theta + \delta\theta_i) - \epsilon_c(\theta)) / \delta\theta_i$, where j_i represents the i -th column of the sensitivity matrix. Before that, however, the proper spatial correspondence between the locations of DIC acquisition points and the integration points of the FE model must be established. Thus, the strain associated with each facet (DIC measured point) $\epsilon_c(\theta)$ is interpolated as the mean strain of the FEM points which lie in the individual facet region.

4. Coefficient matrix

We use Eq. (5) to calculate the coefficient matrix $\mathbf{K} = (\mathbf{J}^T \cdot \mathbf{J})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{J}^T$.

5. MC simulations

Using the probability distributions \mathcal{D}_μ and \mathcal{D}_σ from the 2nd step, we perform MC simulations to assess how the errors propagate to the material parameters. In each iteration we generate random errors e (as shown by Fig. 5) and calculate the variation of the parameters as $\Delta\theta = \mathbf{K} \cdot e$.

6. MOE computation

The previous step yields a large population of calculated material parameters' variations $\Delta\theta$. By calculating the MOE of the distribution with 68.3 % confidence, we get an estimate of standard error for the material parameters.

3. Results – application to open-hole test

We elected to demonstrate the procedure using an open-hole test conducted according to the ASTM-D5766 standard [34]. The test is suitable for testing epoxy unidirectional composites, with orthotropic elastic response where all in-plane stiffness components are affected by

the content and orientation of fibres. The specimens are prescribed to be 60 mm long, 25.4 mm wide and 2.0 mm thick with a 4.2 mm (diameter) hole in the centre.

We measured the strain fields at maximum permissible load (5 kN, prior to the onset of damage) and compared these with the simulated results. The Finite Element (FE) mesh used in the simulation is assumed to be sufficiently dense to keep the numerical error minimal (approximately 300,000 quadrilateral plane stress elements were utilized). Minimizing the discrepancy between the measured and simulated strains leads us to the optimal material parameters, whose confidence intervals we aim to assess. In our study, the optimal parameters obtained via the FEMU identification procedure applied to the open hole experiments (Sect. 4) were $\tilde{\theta} = \{E_{xx}, E_{yy}, G, \nu\} = \{123\text{GPa}, 7.0\text{GPa}, 7.7\text{GPa}, 0.22\}$.

The numerical simulation of the open-hole test was used to calculate the Jacobian matrix (Eq. (5)) for the strain field acquisition points, which are assumed to be located at the centre of each facet. The facet size is set to 19 px with a grid spacing (or step size) of 15 px; these values are characteristic of our history of measurements, which means that the open-hole tensile test was conducted with a speckle size that is most prevalent in the experimental data base. The Jacobian matrix was calculated numerically using finite differences where the variation of the parameters was set to $\tilde{\delta\theta}_i = 10^{-4} \times \tilde{\theta}_i$. The population of material parameters' variations $\Delta\tilde{\theta}$ is calculated (c.f. Fig. 4), with the probability distributions presented in Fig. 6.

As seen in the figure, the population of material parameters' variations $\Delta\tilde{\theta}$ does not follow the Gaussian distribution, since the bias is modelled as means of the errors \mathcal{S}_μ in the MC simulations. This indicates that the bias has a substantial impact on the predicted intervals. Evaluating the MOE of the distributions with 68.3 % confidence, we obtain relative values of $\text{MOE}(\tilde{\theta}) = \{13.3, 22.2, 11.6, 74.6\} \%$.

4. Numerical verification by virtual experimentation

To verify the assumptions in the proposed procedure, such as the linearization of the nonlinear LSQ optimisation problem, we performed the FEMU optimisation procedure using virtual experiments. The strain fields calculated with FEM form the basis for the virtual experimentation. First, we introduced the systematic and random errors determined in Section 2 into the strain fields. The contaminated strain fields were subsequently used as the “measured” ones to identify the material parameters. The discrepancy between the identified parameters and the parameters used in the FEM calculation directly represents the parameter errors due solely to the strain errors.

Since the simulations were carried out using FEM, the results could contain some numerical errors due to discretization and approximation over each finite element. However, since we used an implicit FEM solver, all the equations of the boundary value problem, such as equilibrium and constitutive equations, are iteratively solved to very strict tolerances, which are the same order of magnitude as machine precision. To sum up, simulations are performed in virtual environment and provide a deterministic output, so simulation errors are small in comparison to experimental fluctuations.

Firstly, the measured strain fields were recreated based on the results

of FE simulation of the orthotropic open-hole test. The simulation was performed using Abaqus/Standard. The specimen, the geometry of which is shown in Fig. 7b, was modelled using an orthotropic elastic material model with the reference material parameters $\{E_{xx}, E_{yy}, G, \nu\} = \{123\text{GPa}, 7.0\text{GPa}, 7.7\text{GPa}, 0.22\}$. The FE mesh consisted of approx. 250,000 continuum plane strain CPS4R elements.

The calculated strain fields (Fig. 7c) from these simulations were then intentionally “polluted” with systematic and random errors (Fig. 7d). These errors were generated based on the two-stage error propagation model using the distribution laws presented in Section 2.1. Treating the polluted strain fields as the measured ones, we perform a classical FEMU identification procedure to identify the material parameters. As expected, the identified parameters are slightly different from the reference parameters, due to the error pollution. To obtain a population of the identified parameters, we execute 140 virtual experiments as shown with the “new synthetic experiment” loop shown in Fig. 8. For each virtual experiment we pollute the FEM determined strain field with new generated systematic and random errors. After 140 virtual experiments we get a population of 140 identified material parameters, which is used to calculate the MOE for each parameter.

The presented validation procedure is highly computationally expensive. Assuming that the average identification procedure needs 6 iterations of the FEMU loop to find the optimal values of the material parameters, the presented 140 virtual experiments require 840 FEMU simulations. Moreover, each FEMU iteration needs 1 + no. of parameters FE simulations, if a gradient based optimization method (e.g., Gauss-Newton) is used. The presented case thus needed approximately 4200 FE simulations to calculate the relative values of MOE of the parameters equal to $\text{MOE}(\tilde{\theta}) = \{24.1, 31.5, 15.9, 51.9\} \%$.

5. Experimental validation

Finally, the predicted confidence intervals were experimentally validated by conducting an actual open-hole experiment according to the procedure shown in Fig. 9. We conducted 140 repetitions of the same experiment, except each time, the complete DIC setup was disassembled and reassembled for the next experiment. As stipulated by the measuring protocol, the DIC setup (illumination, position and orientation of cameras, focal length, specimen random pattern preparation, clamping and position of the specimen, the magnitude of preload, field of view, faces size, grid spacing...) was set differently each time with the variety of setup settings constrained to provide consistent results. All unwanted effects (e.g., specimen clamping, preload) that we knew would impair the quality of the results were minimised. The typical range of the parameters is given in Table 1. It should be noted that we were unable to determine the range of some of the parameters, since they were not fully controlled (e.g., speckle pattern).

Each specimen was loaded up to a maximum force of 5 kN, at which point we measured the strain field. Fig. 10 presents our typical experimental setup, with the FOV shown in the centre of the specimen. An example of typically measured strain fields is shown in Fig. 11.

Finally, with the measured strains given, the FEMU identification procedure was conducted separately for each experiment. In a single load step FEMU simulation, we assumed force-driven boundary conditions (see Fig. 7), which follow the prescribed force profile. It should be

Fig. 6. Probability distributions of variations of the orthotropic material parameters $\{E_{xx}, E_{yy}, G, \nu\}$ identified according to the proposed procedure.

Fig. 7. Virtual experiment: (a) specimen, (b) boundary conditions, (c) calculated and (d) polluted longitudinal strain field.

Fig. 8. Flowchart of the validation procedure: FEMU identification procedure is performed for each virtual experiment, polluted with errors determined according to the proposed procedure. The result is a population of the identified material parameters.

Fig. 9. Flowchart of the experimental validation procedure: for each experiment, the DIC setup is changed and recalibrated, the specimen loaded and the strain fields measured. A FEMU identification procedure is then performed for each experiment. As a result, a population of the identified material parameters is obtained.

mentioned that the simulation accounts for ideal boundary condition, specimen alignment and the loading force value, which may include error in real measurement. The 140 inverse identification runs yield a population of identified parameters with a scatter, presented as histograms in Fig. 12. Again, when estimating the relative values of MOE, the following values $MOE(\tilde{\theta}_{exp}) = \{9.87, 38.8, 11.1, 35.1\} \%$ were obtained.

6. Discussion

Let us analyse the margin of error of the material parameters for the analysed full-field experiment and material model. The estimation of confidence intervals for these parameters has been conventionally approached by computing the variance of random errors and their propagation throughout the identification procedure as presented in Appendix A [33]. This prevailing methodology assumes that the measurement errors conform to a normal distribution and are uncorrelated. However, it is crucial to critically examine whether such an approach is sufficiently representative. Following this approach, we conducted an analysis of our past measurements and determined the resulting MOE values, which ranged from 0.6 % to 3 % (Table 2, 1st row). While these values may initially appear promising, it is essential to scrutinize the validity of combining all errors, both random and systematic, into a single population without considering any correlation between experiments.

In this work, on the other hand, we opted for a typical “brute force”, top-down approach by conducting actual experiments in which we measured the strain fields and used them to inversely identify the material parameters. In total, we performed 140 independent experiments employing a stereo-DIC settings that varied within a constrained range. By utilizing the FEMU method, we identified the material parameters and obtained the MOE values ranging from 10 % to 39 % (Table 2, 2nd row). Comparing these values with the MOEs computed using the variance of random errors from the previous paragraph, we observe significantly larger intervals. This substantial discrepancy indicates that the assumption of uncorrelated errors following a normal distribution is incorrect. The identification process based on the actual measurements of 140 strain fields utilizes the FEMU method to calculate the optimal material parameters for each individual specimen. It is worth noting the computational burden associated with this approach. Each iteration of the gradient-based optimization algorithm requires five FEM analyses for four material parameters, and on average, each FEMU identification necessitates six iterations of FEM analysis per experiment. A quick calculation for 140 experiments demonstrates that this approach requires 4200 time-consuming FE simulations, which makes it impractical.

When examining the archive of past DIC measurements in Sect. 2.1, it becomes apparent that the errors associated with each measurement can be divided into the systematic (bias) and random (noise) error. By employing separate probability distributions for these systematic and

Table 1
The stereo-DIC settings and experimental input data for open-hole tests.

Equipment	Specifications
cameras	Manta G-201B, Allied Vision, (Exton, PA, USA) (2 pieces)
image resolution	1624 × 1234 pixel
objective focal distance	35 mm
field of view	from 21 × 16 mm to 28 × 21 mm
stereo angle	from 30° to 50°
illumination colour	from 3200 K to 5600 K
temperature	
patterning technique	black composite surface with white speckles (airbrush)
pattern feature size (approx.)	3 pixels
DIC technique	stereo
DIC software	Istra 4D (ver. 4.6), Dantec Dynamics GmbH, (Ulm, Germany)
facet size	from 15 to 21 pixel
grid spacing	from 12 to 19 pixel
spatial smoothing	none
temporal smoothing	none
number of acq. data points	approx. 5000
acquisition frequency	5 Hz
specimen width	25.4 mm
specimen length (between jaws)	60 mm
specimen thickness	2.0 mm
specimen hole diameter	4.2 mm
loading speed	0.1 mm/min

Fig. 10. Typical experimental setup, with marked field of view.

Fig. 11. An example of measured strain fields: (a) longitudinal, (b) transverse and (c) shear strain.

noise errors, we can effectively model the correlated nature of the measurement error. Using a 'virtual experimentation' approach, as outlined in Sect. 4, we calculated MOE values ranging from 16 % to 52 % (Table 2, 3rd row). These MOE values align reasonably well with the experimentally determined values, confirming the appropriateness of

the error modelling. However, it is important to acknowledge that the discrepancy observed could potentially be attributed to the FEMU method itself, as its performance is highly reliant on the optimization algorithm employed, which may result in suboptimal determination of the material parameters. It is worth noting that the computational burden required for this virtual experiment approach is comparable to the previously described identification from the actual measured responses of 140 experiments (equivalent to 4200 FEM simulations).

To alleviate the computational burden while preserving the concept of separate probability modelling for systematic and noise errors (Sect. 2.1), we propose the method outlined in this paper. By utilizing a linearized coefficient matrix, we can calculate the variations of the material parameters through a simple multiplication (Eq. (5)). By incorporating Monte Carlo simulations, we can estimate the MOE for the material parameters. In the specific case presented, we obtained MOE values ranging from 12 % to 75 % (Table 2, 4th row). The MOE values for the longitudinal elastic modulus E_1 and the shear modulus G closely align with the experimentally determined values. However, there is some discrepancy observed in the MOE values for the transverse elastic modulus E_2 and the Poisson coefficient ν when compared to the values identified from the actual experiments. It is important to note that certain discrepancies are expected due to the linearization process and the optimization procedures described earlier, which may not always produce optimal identification results. The presented method is computationally efficient, requiring only 1 + no. of parameters finite element simulations and a few thousand Monte-Carlo iterations involving random sampling.

A final noteworthy observation is that all the methods employed consistently exhibit lower reliability in identifying the transverse elastic modulus E_{yy} compared to the longitudinal modulus E_{xx} . Additionally, the Poisson coefficient ν is identified with the lowest level of confidence. This lower confidence can be attributed to the less pronounced transverse contraction of the specimen and thus comparatively less essential information available for accurate identification.

7. Conclusions

In the context of inverse material parameter identification from stereo-DIC measurements, our approach offers a practical and efficient means of assessing the parameter confidence intervals. Unlike the traditional bottom-up approach, which involves labour-intensive error source analysis and a great deal of experimental effort, our two-stage error propagation model presents a more streamlined method. By utilizing Monte Carlo simulations and analysing existing stereo-DIC measurements, we pre-evaluate confidence intervals. Our methodology not only saves time but also provides a unique advantage by considering variations in strain measurement errors, challenging the traditional Gaussian assumption. Classical analysis tends to produce overly narrow confidence intervals and is impractical for multiple measurement repetitions due to their time and resource intensity.

A notable feature setting our methodology apart from other models is its ability to estimate confidence intervals before conducting experiments. It relies on a pre-existing database of strain measurements, typically archived by the experimentalists. While the quality of this database affects the results, improvements can be made through employing experiment-optimised databases or by utilizing better DIC equipment, such as higher-resolution cameras.

In the future, the proposed method can be adapted to treat random and systematic errors separately. For example, by having several initial samples (photos) for the baseline "unloaded" state, each introducing slightly different random errors. One approach would be to take several initial measurements, turning the equipment on and off, reattaching the sample, recalibrating and repositioning cameras, lamps, etc. after each one. It could also be useful to introduce additional parameters to the method for vibration analysis [46–48].

In summary: by leveraging past strain measurements and accounting

Fig.12. Probability distributions of variations of the orthotropic material parameters $\{E_{xx}, E_{yy}, G, \nu\}$ identified from the experimental verification data.

Table 2
Calculated Margins of Error with 68.3 % confidence based on different methods.

Method	MOE(E_1) (%)	MOE(E_2) (%)	MOE(G) (%)	MOE(ν) (%)	No. of FEM simulations
COV($\hat{\theta}$) (Appendix A)	0.6	2.2	3.0	1.2	5
Experimental validation (Sect. 5)	9.9	38.8	11.1	35.1	4200
Numerical verification (Sect. 4)	24.1	31.5	15.9	51.9	4200
Proposed method (Sect. 3)	13.3	22.2	11.6	74.6	5

for systematic and random errors in the DIC system, our approach provides a practical means of estimating parameter uncertainty in stereo-DIC experiments. This information allows researchers to make informed decisions about specimen design and experiment optimization, ultimately enhancing the quality of material identification.

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Author statement

We confirm that the manuscript has been read and approved by all named authors and that there are no other persons who satisfied the

Appendix A: Prediction according to the Gaussian model error

It is interesting to observe the history of our measurements if we assume that we are unaware of systematic and random error and combine all measurements over past years and all strain field acquisition points (i.e. the same data as in Sect. 2.1) into a single population of the measurements. This way, we obtain a population of strain errors that closely follow the Gaussian distribution of errors as presented in Fig. A.1.

Fig.A.1. Probability distribution of measuring errors sampled over different specimens, and acquisition points (fields) combined into a single population. The solid line presents a fit with the Gaussian distribution.

Taking into account that the errors follow the Gaussian distribution and assuming that the errors are uncorrelated, we can compute the variance of

criteria for authorship but are not listed. We further confirm that the order of authors listed in the manuscript has been approved by all of us.

We understand that the Corresponding Author is the sole contractor for the Editorial process. He is responsible for communicating with the other authors about the progress, submissions of revisions and final approval of proofs.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Andraž Maček: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Bojan Starman:** Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Sam Coppiters:** Validation, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Janez Urevc:** Software, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Miroslav Halilović:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Resources, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The raw/processed data required to reproduce these findings cannot be shared at this time, as the data also forms part of an ongoing study. They will, however, subsequently be made available on individual request.

the random error [33] to estimate the MOE of the material parameters. The approach is straightforward as it is based on an (linear) error propagation model. As shown in Fig. A.2, the parameter’s MOE are calculated as a solution to an eigenvalue problem and are dependent only on the measurement error and the sensitivity matrix. To calculate it, we need to perform only $1 + n$ FEM simulations, where n represents the number of material parameters. For our open-hole case, the analytical method returns the coefficient of variation equal to $COV(\tilde{\theta}) = \{0.63, 2.24, 3.04, 1.22\}\%$.

Fig.A.2. Flowchart of the parameter uncertainty prediction according to the Gaussian model error: since the errors are assumed to be normally distributed and uncorrelated at pixel scale, the parameter covariance (uncertainty) is calculated using the sensitivity matrix and an eigenvalue problem.

Appendix B: Table of the identified material parameters in the open-hole experimental validation

In the process of experimental validation (Sect. 5) we conducted 140 individual open-hole experiments. For each experiment we identified the orthotropic elastic material parameters, which are summarized with histograms in Fig. 10. The individual material parameters identified are listed in Table B.1.

Table B.1
The identified material parameters in the open-hole experimental validation.

No.	E_1 (MPa)	E_2 (MPa)	G (MPa)	ν (/)	No.	E_1 (MPa)	E_2 (MPa)	G (MPa)	ν (/)	No.	E_1 (MPa)	E_2 (MPa)	G (MPa)	ν (/)
1	130,526	5421	10,143	0.217	48	108,929	6643	8000	0.184	95	120,816	7547	7679	0.187
2	128,889	5000	8111	0.231	49	113,068	7726	7550	0.180	96	127,595	8800	7486	0.201
3	123,721	5400	7293	0.237	50	112,100	8263	7679	0.216	97	115,789	8158	8429	0.184
4	136,667	4000	8889	0.358	51	116,942	8084	7421	0.201	98	123,158	7474	9286	0.184
5	137,895	5421	8000	0.381	52	129,364	7571	9364	0.154	99	113,333	5000	5778	0.147
6	146,071	2000	7727	0.217	53	116,942	8084	7679	0.251	100	112,105	7474	6286	0.283
7	128,563	5579	8000	0.259	54	123,158	5421	8429	0.283	101	127,595	7368	7614	0.266
8	127,500	4786	7571	0.283	55	110,714	4786	7571	0.244	102	106,786	5714	7571	0.206
9	160,000	1000	5000	0.400	56	126,626	7189	7357	0.280	103	114,037	8800	7807	0.194
10	140,000	6643	8273	0.322	57	125,658	7011	7614	0.273	104	113,068	8621	7614	0.251
11	118,571	2929	7143	0.206	58	105,909	7909	8000	0.234	105	124,689	8442	7100	0.223
12	130,526	3368	7143	0.217	59	106,786	10,357	8000	0.283	106	118,571	9429	8429	0.206
13	132,143	9091	9364	0.316	60	97,368	6105	8429	0.217	107	121,784	7011	7421	0.223
14	138,214	3857	7571	0.206	61	123,158	7474	8857	0.184	108	122,500	11,286	8000	0.128
15	128,889	5000	8111	0.273	62	122,273	6643	7727	0.154	109	115,974	6653	7229	0.201
16	134,211	2000	5000	0.184	63	128,563	8800	7421	0.194	110	116,942	5758	7229	0.273
17	134,211	6789	8429	0.184	64	123,721	6116	7807	0.223	111	118,214	9429	8429	0.184
18	134,286	3857	7143	0.206	65	130,500	8263	7679	0.266	112	108,421	6789	7143	0.184
19	123,158	5421	10,571	0.250	66	123,158	8158	7143	0.349	113	90,000	8158	6714	0.086
20	140,000	2929	7727	0.255	67	130,500	6474	7100	0.280	114	115,789	10,211	6714	0.283
21	137,895	4053	9286	0.316	68	130,357	9429	7571	0.244	115	108,421	8842	6714	0.053
22	130,357	2929	8429	0.128	69	130,526	6789	7571	0.349	116	101,053	7474	6714	0.119
23	129,364	6643	8818	0.221	70	136,786	9429	8000	0.283	117	108,421	6789	5857	0.151
24	132,909	3857	8273	0.322	71	108,421	8842	8000	0.250	118	106,786	7571	6286	0.128
25	136,786	2000	6286	0.217	72	132,909	7571	7727	0.356	119	110,714	6643	7143	0.167
26	115,182	4786	7727	0.154	73	137,895	8842	8000	0.349	120	101,909	7571	7182	0.154
27	128,563	5937	7100	0.259	74	115,789	10,895	7571	0.316	121	108,929	4364	6091	0.250
28	125,818	2929	7727	0.087	75	141,579	5421	9714	0.349	122	104,636	6643	7727	0.121
29	114,643	3857	6714	0.167	76	130,526	7474	6714	0.316	123	105,545	9429	6091	0.188
30	126,842	3368	8857	0.316	77	137,895	6789	10,143	0.283	124	113,571	11,286	7571	0.151
31	129,364	9429	7727	0.289	78	126,842	10,211	8000	0.349	125	118,214	4364	6636	0.283
32	137,895	2684	8000	0.283	79	106,455	5714	7727	0.221	126	112,100	7011	8000	0.187
33	130,357	3857	7571	0.283	80	108,929	12,636	9909	0.217	127	110,091	10,357	7182	0.154
34	136,786	2000	6714	0.151	81	141,429	5714	8000	0.349	128	118,879	7726	7100	0.280
35	105,909	6182	7500	0.148	82	124,689	5758	8000	0.280	129	132,143	7909	8273	0.217
36	118,727	8500	8273	0.121	83	136,667	6000	8889	0.316	130	115,182	10,357	7727	0.154
37	122,857	3182	7727	0.151	84	127,500	8500	7571	0.316	131	122,273	6643	6636	0.289
38	137,895	5421	8000	0.316	85	134,211	9526	7143	0.349	132	115,182	10,357	7727	0.188
39	130,500	5400	7421	0.201	86	134,211	7474	6714	0.283	133	119,847	7547	7550	0.216
40	118,727	4786	6636	0.121	87	115,789	7474	6714	0.349	134	101,909	14,071	8818	0.188
41	118,727	2929	6091	0.154	88	110,714	9429	8857	0.244	135	125,818	7571	8273	0.255
42	103,182	6182	8000	0.105	89	126,429	10,357	9286	0.283	136	110,714	8500	7571	0.244
43	113,333	10,000	7333	0.147	90	118,879	8800	7100	0.216	137	130,357	8500	6286	0.361
44	111,636	5714	7727	0.154	91	126,429	10,357	8000	0.244	138	124,692	6646	6634	0.264
45	118,571	3857	8000	0.089	92	130,526	10,895	8857	0.151	139	112,108	9423	7612	0.186
46	118,571	10,357	8857	0.206	93	116,942	8800	8000	0.230	140	126,629	10,359	6639	0.314
47	115,974	6474	7229	0.216	94	122,273	9429	7727	0.255					

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